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Who is the lone terrorist? A study of Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

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Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

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Abstract

Lone actor terrorism has become a significant challenge for Western democracies. Previous studies have failed to point out a comprehensive profile of lone terrorists, and suggested that examining more specific sub-groups of lone actors, sharing contextual factors or ideology, may produce such a profile. The current study examines the sub-group of Vehicle-Borne lone terrorists, who committed their attacks in Israel and the West-Bank between January 2000 and March 2016. Based on confidential and open-source data, we find that general socio-demographic characteristics did not produce a unique profile of attackers. However, a deeper examination of behavioural factors preceding the attack yields common traits. Specifically, we find that previous experience – both in different forms of unlawful behaviour and in training related to the attack method – was significantly related to a successful attack. Similarities in regards to the triggers for the attack and personal motivations also emerge, suggesting that while operating independently, lone actors are very much influenced by on-going events. We conclude that focusing on a subgroup of lone attackers following a spatio-methodological oriented approach contributes to the construction of a profile for lone terrorists, and discuss these findings in the context of mitigation.

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Introduction

On 14 July 2016, at the height of French Bastille Day celebrations, a 31-year-old lone terrorist named Mohamed Lahouaiej-Bouhlel drove a truck into a crowd in the city of Nice, France. As a result, 86 people were killed and 302 injured, making the events in Nice the most brutal Vehicle-Borne attack to occur on European ground. While the attack in Nice may be considered exceptional with regard to the number of casualties, Vehicle-Borne terrorist attacks are not a new strategy for lone-actor terrorists. In 2017, vehicle-borne attacks have resulted in numerous casualties in London, Stockholm and Berlin; past attacks were documented in France (2014, 2016), Germany (2016), Canada (2014), the UK (2016), and Israel. The popularity of this modus operandi among lone actors is not surprising, as vehicles are an effective and relatively simple attack method, requiring minimal resources and planning. Alongside the relative effectiveness and simplicity of this method, it has also been widely legitimized by terrorist organisations: for example, a senior ISIS leader, Abu Mohammed al-Adnani, urged supporters of the terror group to “run over” the “filthy French” two years before the Nice attack¹.

Terrorist attacks by lone actors have become more widespread in numbers and locations over the past few decades². Attacks committed by individuals, with no organisational background and support, are considered more difficult to prevent and mitigate as compared to “classic” organisational terrorism. This is because lone attacks involve less communication, preparation and other activities that are likely to be spotted by efficient intelligence agencies prior to the event. At the same time, lone attacks can be as effective as organised terrorism, resulting in a large number of casualties (as mentioned earlier in Nice) and altering everyday life in European cities.

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The inherent challenges encompassed in lone actor terrorism, as well as their destructive nature, highlight the need for empirical research focusing on this growing phenomenon. Accordingly, scholars and think-tanks are encouraged to come up with a comprehensive profile of lone actors that could be spotted and detected before the attack³. Several attempts have been made to produce such a profile, all advocating for a lack of similar traits, due to heterogeneity in ideology, situational factors, motivation and characteristics⁴. In the last decade, scholars have emphasized the need to empirically examine not the entire population of lone-actor terrorists, but specific sub-groups, sharing ideology and contextual circumstances, in the effort to produce such a profile⁵. The importance of pointing out the common traits for specific groups of lone-actors is twofold: first, advancing the theoretical understanding of nonorganizational terrorism, and second, allowing the identification of group-relevant intervention points for mitigation.

In light of the growing numbers of vehicle-borne attacks by lone terrorists, the current study aims to inform the understanding, countering and mitigating of such attacks. Following the literature suggesting focusing on smaller sub-groups of lone actors to produce a profile, we examine the population of lone-actor vehicle-borne attacks carried out in Israel between January 2000 and March 2016. Using confidential data from the Israeli Security Agency, court files, and open-source data from media and social networks, we analyse the socio-demographic characteristics, unlawful behaviour, motivation, and triggers of 62 vehicle-borne lone attackers, to examine whether focusing on a sub-group of lone actors with similar ideology, attack method and location is indeed effective in producing a profile.

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First, we discuss lone-actor terrorism, with special focus on previous attempts to discern the profile of lone-attackers. We then move on to discuss lone-actor vehicle-borne attacks as a method of terrorism in Israel and the West Bank, and explain the research approach, data collection, and methodology. Finally, the findings are presented and detailed within the framework of lone-actor terrorism prevention, as we discuss policy implications and the limitations of the study.

Lone-actor terrorism

There has been much ambiguity in the literature regarding the definition of lone-actors in terrorism. While some have referred only to individuals acting entirely on their own, others have included terrorists who received moral, or even technical support from organisations in different stages of attack planning, or that operated in pairs or small groups⁶. For the purpose of the current study, a lone-actor terrorist is defined as an unaffiliated individual who “acts on his or her own without orders from—or even connections to—an organization”⁷. Two additional considerations to this definition should be noted: First, while a lone actor is not related to an organization, he or she may collaborate with other individuals⁸. Second, lone actors may be inspired by the actions or the ideology of an organization (very often on-line), without being in direct contact with any of its members⁹. In other words, while lone actors are not part of a larger terrorist network, they are not necessarily isolated.

Acts of terrorism planned and executed by a single predator are becoming more and more common in Western democracies and have been widely encouraged by a variety of ideological backgrounds, including, but not limited to, Salafi-Jihadi

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Islam¹⁰. While lone-wolf events are still the minority of terrorist attacks, they pose a significant threat to law enforcement agencies, as the solitude of the behaviour rarely permit to trace and prevent potential attacks. No direct communication with known networks, no involvement of others, and limited pursuit of illegal resources mean that intelligence agencies cannot rely of the ‘traditional giveaways’ used in the case of organized terrorism. As a result, significant efforts have been invested in discerning a profile, or common traits, of lone-actor terrorists that will enable agencies to point out specific people as potential threat¹¹.

Is there a profile for lone actors?

There seems to be a consensus among scholars on the lack of a single comprehensive profile for lone-actor terrorists¹². Some very basic traits do emerge: attackers tend to be male, under 50 years old, who use firearms¹³ or explosives against civilian targets¹⁴. However, these traits are hardly enough to differentiate lone actors from any other population of criminal offenders¹⁵.

The lack of a profile is also apparent when examining common traits in regard to ideologies and motivations¹⁶. Some lone attackers are connected to or inspired by wider networks, while others act in complete independence¹⁷; some have suffered from a history of mental problems¹⁸, while others did not demonstrate such behaviour¹⁹; and they show very different levels, if any, of social isolation²⁰.

How can this lack of a profile for lone actors be accounted for? One important reason is heterogeneity – in backgrounds, ideology and contextual factors²¹. Lone actors are operating in very different geographical, legal and political environments, are motivated by right-wing, left-wing or religious ideologies, and are inspired by

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different religious groups or terrorists' organizations. For example, comparing the profiles of Mir Aimal Kansi, a Pakistani national who shot CIA employees in their cars on 1993; David Copeland, who used bombs against Blacks, Asians and Gays in London in 1999; and Yigal Amir, who shot and murder the Israeli Prime Minister Yitzchak Rabin in 1995, will produce very little similarity. Alongside the prominent heterogeneity and important differences in contextual factors, another reason for the absence of a profile is the fact that lone-actor incidents are a very small fraction of terrorism²². This makes lone actors a statistically *quantité négligable* phenomena, and hence it is difficult to trace any similarities between cases, even when those do exist. Moreover, most of the studies on lone-actor terrorism are based on open-source data, which is often very limited, especially in regard to information on the attackers²³. Much of the important research done in this field is based on case studies or nonrepresentative samples, rather than large random sampling, leaving limited possibilities to empirical comparison²⁴.

Arguably, the most comprehensive study of lone-actor terrorists was conducted by Paul Gill²⁵. Based on a systematic analysis of 119 lone-actor cases from the US and Europe, Gill examined their personal socio-demographic characteristics, motivation and cooperation with others and wider networks. Gill's offenders acted on behalf of diverse ideologies, from Al-Qaida to environmental causes; their age ranged from 15 to 69 years, with a mean of 33. Many, but not all lone-actor terrorists were socially isolated: half were single individuals who had never married, 31% were married or in a relationship, and 18.9% were separated or divorced (15.1%). They had relatively high educational achievements, with all of them attending secondary school, and 54.6% attending or completing some sort of higher education; however,

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many of them (40.2%) were unemployed, and most of the rest worked as service providers or in manual labour. A quarter of Gill's offenders had military experience, and 41.2% were previously involved in unlawful behaviour. A large proportion of the sample (31.9%) had a known history of mental health problems. Gill concludes this comprehensive analysis by stating that "There was no uniform profile of lone-actor terrorists"²⁶.

While the studies mentioned above clearly indicate the lack of a general profile for lone-actor terrorists, scholars suggest that more specific groups of lone actors may demonstrate such a profile²⁷. For example, Sageman²⁸ suggested differentiating "real lone actors" who are often motivationally inspired by a virtual community²⁹ from mass-murderers. McCauley and Moskalenko³⁰ suggested dividing lone actors into two groups: disconnected-disordered individuals with a grievance and weapons experience, who are social loners and often show signs of psychological disorder; and caring-compelled ones, who strongly feel the suffering of others and sense a personal responsibility to reduce or avenge this suffering. Bakker and De Graaf³¹ emphasized the variations in target selection, modus operandi, ideological background and motivations among lone actors. They suggested that lone actors can be divided into categories, based on their ideology or religious background.

Similarly, Pantucci³² stressed the importance of distinguishing lone actors who are motivated by a personal grievance³³ from those who follow a "real" ideology: "people who get involved in ideological terrorism alone and lone individuals who for their own reasons seek to express rage"³⁴. He then continued to describe four types of lone actors: (1) the loner – isolated individuals, not inspired by or related to any

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network, using ideology as a justification for their attack; (2) lone wolves – individuals who carry out the attack alone, but are supported by or connected to others; (3) the lone-wolf pack – a group of individuals, going together through a process of self-radicalization to become ideologically motivated; and (4) lone attackers, who operate with direct support and operational control, but execute the final act alone. However, while Pantucci provides examples for each of these categories, he does not offer a systematic examination of the profile or motivation of each of these types.

Few empirical studies have followed this approach and indeed found some common traits when examining specific sub-groups of lone attackers. Gill³⁵ compared sub-groups of attackers based on ideology and stated that despite the diversity of loneactor terrorists, there were distinguishable differences between subgroups. Similarly, De Roy van Zuijdewijn and Bakker³⁶ examined 120 lone actors involved in terrorism in the European Union between 2000 and 2014. They found significant differences in socio-demographic characteristics and in motivation for lone actors belonging to different age groups, or acting on behalf of different ideologies. These findings suggest that concentrating on a more specific group of lone actors – sharing contextual circumstances, ideology and modus operandi – may increase our ability to discern a profile of lone-actor terrorists, providing a basis for intervention.

In this regard, Clarke and Newman³⁷ suggested that decisions made by terrorists are determined by situational contingencies and limitations. The resulting incentives and opportunities are unique to a specific type of offense and its contextual circumstances³⁸. Therefore it is recommended that researchers study the terrorists' strategies and specific attack plans by analysing the methods, mechanisms, and

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procedures involved in specific methodologies of terrorist attacks³⁹. However, to the best of our knowledge, the profile of sub-groups of lone-actors who share an attack modus operandi has not yet been examined.

Case study: Lone-actor Vehicle-Borne attacks in Israel and the West Bank

The current study follows the propositions made by Borum et al.⁴⁰ and Clarke and Newman⁴¹, to focus on specific, method-based sub-groups of lone-attackers, by examining the population of lone actors who committed Vehicle-Borne attacks in Israel and the West Bank between January 2000 and March 2016. Three reasons have led us to choose Vehicle-Borne attacks as our main focus of analysis: first, Vehicle-Borne attacks are a classic lone actors' modus operandi. Out of 62 Vehicle-Borne attacks that took place in Israel and the West Bank between January 2000 and March 2016, none were committed by a terrorist organization. Moreover, the tendency of lone attackers to choose this method of attack seems to spread beyond the geographical and contextual boundaries of the Middle-East, as recent vehicle-borne attacks in the UK, France, Germany and Stockholm all represent non-organized terrorism. As mentioned above, this tendency of lone attackers to choose a vehicle as their weapon is both the result of the relative simplicity and practicality of this method, and of the legitimization this technique has received in the Salafi-Jihadi context.

The second reason for focusing on vehicle-borne terrorism has to do with the quality of the data: most of the run-over cases in Israel result with a clear identification of the attacker, when he or she are killed or arrested. The positive identification of the attacker contributes to the amount of data available on each case,

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permitting a more comprehensive analysis of both the attacker and the environmental conditions related to the attack.

Last, while Vehicle-Borne attacks have mainly occurred in Israel and the West Bank, this method is rapidly spreading across Europe. The severe consequences of recent Vehicle-Borne attacks in Nice, France and Berlin, Germany emphasize the importance of studying and modelling this method, to point out possible pinch points for intervention. But while other methods of terrorist attacks, employing, for example, armed weapons or explosives, have been widely studied⁴², we are not aware of any other study examining this specific *modus operandi*.

As for the decision to choose Israel as our study location, this was driven by the large number of lone actor vehicle-borne attacks occurring in Israel over the past two decades. While, as mentioned, vehicle-borne terrorism is rapidly becoming common on European grounds, it is still a relatively new and rare *modus operandi*. In Israel, run-over attacks have been common in the last years, and even more popular in the last wave of terrorism in 2015-2016. The large number of attacks, the richness of data on the attackers, and the accumulated knowledge on this method of terrorism, have made Israel and the West-Bank a suitable location for this kind of analysis, allowing us to draw conclusions that may be helpful in developing intervention strategies both inside and outside of the Israeli/Middle East geographical context.

Methodology

Study population

The current study analyse the population of vehicle-borne terrorist attacks committed by lone-actor predators In Israel and the West Bank, between January 2000

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and March 2016. It is important to note that in contrast to most studies on lone actor terrorism, this analysis is not based on a sample of cases, but rather on all vehicle-borne attacks during this period.

The population of attacks in this period includes 62 events, 13 in Israel and 49 in the West Bank, resulting in 27 victims and 253 injured⁴³. Vehicle-borne attacks were not evenly spread during the research period: events since the year 2000 were considered to include the “second Intifada” and the years until 2007, which were characterized by a relatively low popularity of this modus operandi. This changed in 2008, when lone vehicle-borne attacks became more frequent, reaching a peak during the years 2014–2016. In 2015, during a significant wave of terrorist attacks, vehicleborne attacks reached an all-time record of 33 documented events.

Data collection and analysis

The data for this study was obtained from the Israeli Security Agency (ISA) as well as from open sources such as court proceedings and decisions, media and social media (both in Hebrew and in Arabic). In each of the Vehicle-Borne cases, we collected information and examined the following parameters about the attacker: (1) socio-demographic characteristics – name, age, marital status, place of residence, physical and mental health, level of education, employment, financial status; (2) previous involvement in unlawful behaviour – arrests, convictions, imprisonment; and (3) declared (and non-declared) motivations and triggers for the attack. This list of characteristics follows the guidelines suggested by Gill⁴⁴ for the study of lone-actor terrorists. The purpose of this integration is to maximize the external validity of the findings regarding lone actors’ attacks. That being said, several of the original

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variables were customized to better reflect the Israeli context and to allow a more detailed analysis of the vehicle-borne attackers.

Data collected was drawn from three main sources, which together provide a detailed description of the attackers. The bulk of the data was drawn from the files of the Israeli Security Agency (ISA). When available, the data received from the ISA has then been enriched by accessing the court files and proceedings related to the case⁴⁵. The variables retrieved from the court files included further details on the attacker's personal history, previous involvement in terrorism and/or criminal behaviour and triggers for the attack. Finally, the dataset has also been augmented with information gathered from Israeli media reports and relevant internet sources, including social networks⁴⁶ in both Hebrew and Arabic, when these have been used by the attackers or their supporters in relation to the attack⁴⁷. Information retrieved from social networks included statements concerning the motivation and triggers for the attack, as well as previous involvement in unlawful behaviour.

Data collection began in October 2014 and continued until the third quarter of 2016. To ensure that the lists included the entire population of lone-actor cases during the study period (January 2000 to March 2016), the list of cases received from the ISA was compared to media coverage on terrorism. Once the list was complete and parallel to receiving the data on each case from the ISA, court files were matched to the list of lone-actor attacks to enrich the set of variables for quantitative analysis. Four research assistants retrieved the relevant files using Israeli legal databases, matching each case to the relevant file from the ISA list using criteria such as the attacker's name or the date, time and location of the attack. This data was then supplemented by open-source data – media and social network publications regarding

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the relevant cases, retrieved from the internet in both Hebrew and Arabic. All information on the attackers from the different data sources was integrated into one dataset, and analysed using descriptive statistic methods and T-tests. The next section presents the findings of this analysis.

Findings

We divide the findings into three sections. The first section details the findings related to the attackers' socio-demographic characteristics; the second describes any previous involvement in unlawful behaviour, including arrests and imprisonment; and last, we present the findings on the motivations and triggers that have led the attackers to act.

Socio-demographic characteristics

In-line with previous research on lone-actors mentioned above, sociogeographic characteristics by themselves provide only a very general profile of lone vehicle-borne attackers. This “profile” is based mostly on their gender and religious identity: all of the attackers were Muslim - most were religious Muslims (37, or 59.7%), 23 were conservative Muslims (37.1%), and 2 were secular (3.2%). Almost all of them (59, or 95.2%) were male; 3 attacks (4.8%) were carried out by Muslim women. Other personal characteristics do not demonstrate one consistent pattern. As can be seen in Table 1, all of the attackers were adults, as implied by the use of a vehicle as the weapon of choice; the youngest attacker was 18 years old at the time of the attack, and the oldest was 88 years old. Most of the attackers (33, or 53.2%) were between 18

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and 25 years of age; 12 attackers (19.4%) were 26–33 years old; 11 (17.7%) were 34–41 years old; and only 6 attackers (9.7%) were over 42 years old

(see Table 1).

[***Insert Table 1 about here***]

While observing solely socio-demographic characteristics did not produce a distinctive profile, it is important to note that some of the findings challenge the conventional assumption about lone terrorists reflecting a unique loner, isolated character. As can be seen in Table 2, out of 43 Vehicle-Borne attacks for which the personal status of the offender is known, 29 of the attackers (67.4%) were married or living with a partner at the time of the attack, and 23 (37.1%) of the attackers were parents. Only 13 (30.2%) of the Vehicle-Borne attackers were single (21%), and one was widowed (2.3%). These findings are in line with those of Gill, Hogan and Deckert⁴⁸, reflecting very different levels (if any) of social isolation amongst lone terrorist.

[***Insert Table 2 about here***]

Economic desperation or unemployment were most likely not the motivating factors for committing most of the lone vehicle-borne attacks. Almost all of the attackers (53, or 85.4%) were employed, and 64.4% of them had an average or above average socioeconomic status (35 with a medium socioeconomic status, and 5 with a high socioeconomic status). Nineteen attackers had a low socioeconomic status (30.6%), and for 3 (4.8%) there was no record of their financial status. As for the offenders' level of education, out of 26 cases that contained this information, half of the attackers only had primary school education (13 cases, or 50%), and the rest had

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some form of high school education, including 4 (15.4%) attackers with higher education.⁴⁹

Of 44 attackers for whom the specific profession is known, 14 (31.8%) were working as drivers or as heavy equipment operators, 3 were construction workers (6.8%), 18 attackers (40.9%) had other vocations, and 9 attackers were unemployed (20.5%) at the time of the attack. Interestingly, being trained as a professional driver was significantly related to a more successful attack. An independent-samples T-test was conducted to compare the number of injured⁵⁰ in attacks committed by attackers trained as professional drivers as opposed to the number of injured by attackers who were not professionally trained as drivers. There was a significant difference in the scores for professional drivers ($M=7.57$, $SD=9.78$) and non-professional drivers ($M=3.06$, $SD=3.19$); $t(60)=2.77$, $p=0.00$. These results suggest that attacks that were committed by attackers trained as professional drivers led to a larger number of injured.

Criminal background

One of the central findings of the current study is related to attackers' previous involvement in criminal or terrorist activities. A quarter of the attackers (25.8%) had prior criminal records at the time of the attack; Ten of the attackers (16.1%) were previously imprisoned; and 9 of the attackers have previously engaged in terrorist activity (14.5%. see Figure 1).

*****Insert Figure 1 about here*****

Moreover, There was a significant difference in the scores for those who had been involved in criminal activities in the past ($M=5.87$, $SD=7.78$) and those who

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haven't ($M=3.02$, $SD=3.61$); $t(60)=1.96$, $p=0.05$. These results suggest that attacks that were committed by attackers who were previously involved in criminal activities resulted in a larger number of injured.

In addition, we examined whether the attacker had a family member who had a security related or criminal record, and found that 14 attackers had such a relative (22.6%), most being Hamas activists. For the relatives of the other attackers (48, or 77.4%) there was no information indicating such involvement.

Triggers and motivation

To examine the triggers and motivation leading to the attacks, we analysed testimonies from the attackers as well as from their immediate surroundings (family, friends) collected during the investigation immediately after the attack. Triggers and motivation reflected in the attackers' declarations in social media prior to the attack were also considered. Specifically, we looked for any possible motivation or catalyst that may have triggered or encouraged the attack, such as nationalistic/religious perceptions, evidence of mental difficulties (use of drugs, consultations with psychiatrists, hospitalizations or report about severe behavioural disorders), expressions of extreme emotional distress, such as outbreaks of anger, or a family conflict (e.g., an argument with spouse or parents, divorce).

One important similarity emerges from the data regards the declared motivation for the attack – the reason given to the attack by the offenders. More than half of the attackers (35, or 56.5%) carried out the attack with a declared nationalistic/religious drive stemming from a desire to sacrifice themselves, in light of conflict events (for

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example, the war in the Gaza Strip). This was evident both from their declarations in social media, and from the attackers' testimonies in the investigation following the attack.

As for personal motivations or triggers for the attack, in contrast to the conventional assumption that most lone wolves suffer from mental difficulties⁵¹, we have found indications of mental health problems only for 8 attackers (12.9%). For the other 54 attackers (87.1%) we did not find any indications of mental health problems. This finding is in line with those of Bakker and De Graaf and Corner and Gill⁵² that found only a small portion of lone-actors suffers from a history of mental problems. While mental health problems were relatively rare amongst our sample, evidence of extreme emotional distress preceding the attack were more common. For 22 of the offenders (35.5%) there is evidence indicating that the individual was expressing extreme anger at the time leading up to the event. For the other attackers (40, or 64.5%) there is no such evidence. Although not very common, family conflicts were also amongst the triggers leading to the attack: 9 (14.5%) offenders carried out the attack due to personal issues such as involvement in family conflict (e.g., an argument with spouse or parents, divorce) shortly before the attack.

*****Insert Figure 2 about here*****

In addition to the declared motivation for the attack, and the undeclared triggers that may have encourage the attacker to act, we analysed case investigations and court files to identify the “tipping point” preceding the event. In the context of lone-actor terrorist attacks, the term ‘tipping point’ relates to a specific point in the process leading up to the event when the attacker decided to carry out the attack.

While the process of radicalization, the decision to be involved in terrorism and even

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the preparation phase can already take place prior to this point, the tipping point represents the decision to commit a specific, defined act of violence⁵³. This moment of decision can be related to a specific trigger (e.g., the attacker experienced a family conflict, and as a result decided to attack). As can be seen in Figure 2, and consistent with the evidence in the literature describing a specific ‘tipping point’ or a ‘point of no return’ in the build-up to the attack, in almost half of the Vehicle-Borne cases (29, or 47%) we found indications of a known ‘tipping point’ in the progression of the grievance that precipitated the attack.

Discussion and conclusions

The current study analyses the main traits of the population of lone vehicleborne attackers in Israel and the West Bank, from January 2000 to March 2016. To our knowledge, this is the first study to combine confidential and open source data to examine socio-demographic, behavioural and motivational factors as related to vehicle borne attacks.

The first important finding emerging from this analysis is that despite the relative similarity among these offenders in terms of religious background, contextual factors and modus operandi, there is still no one comprehensive socio-demographic unique profile shared by all these predators. Age, education, employment and personal status have all been found to be relatively heterogenic; suggesting that for lone-actors, a similarity in declared ideology and contextual factors does not guaranty similar traits.

However, our findings indicate that common trait do emerge when observing the behavioural factors preceding the attack. Similar to Gill⁵⁴, we find that most of the

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lone actors in our study had some level of previous involvement in unlawful behaviour – either crime or terrorism related offenses. In other words, many of the attackers did not “emerge out of nowhere” as often described in the media, but were already known to law enforcement agencies at the time of the attack, suggesting the possibility of prevention. Moreover, we find that this kind of past involvement in criminal behaviour was significantly related to the results of the attack: Attacks committed by lone vehicle-borne attackers that were previously involved in unlawful behaviour resulted in more injuries than others, committed by first-time offenders. On the theoretical level, this finding re-enforces the conception that lone-actor terrorism is not always an isolated violent action, but may be related to wider traits of behaviour, demonstrated by the attacker’s history⁵⁵. In regard to vehicle-borne attacks, this particular finding can also be translated into practical implications. Many Vehicle-Borne attacks, including the one in Nice, France, are performed by professional drivers that are using their truck or tractor as a weapon of choice. As reflected in our data, the training encompassed in professional driving, and the access to heavy vehicles such as a tractor or truck, were significantly related to a more successful attack and a larger number of injured. Therefore, taking into consideration one’s criminal background when approving professional driving licenses may serve as an important intervention measure, potentially making access to this sort of a weapon more challenging. While this policy may not affect private vehicle attackers, it will assist in the mitigation of the most destructive and significant events.

Additional important similarities emerge from the findings regarding the triggers and motivations for lone vehicle-borne attacks. The first is related to the declared motivation for the attack: almost 60% of the attackers declared that they

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responded to a nationalistic/religious drive, stemming from a desire to sacrifice themselves. This drive was described by the attackers as stemming from recent conflict events, such as the war in the Gaza Strip or changing political circumstances. This suggests that lone actors, who act independently and are neither guided nor controlled by larger networks, also react to political events as a possible source of motivation or an excuse to deal with personal grievances. Such motivations could also be explained by the conclusion of Hamm and Spaaij⁵⁶, that lone-wolf terrorists often act due to a feeling of deprivation of things they believe they are entitled to (on a personal or collective level). On the practical level, this finding suggests that the immediate period shortly after specific political or security-related events (e.g., elections, military operations abroad, and immigration related legislation) should be considered more vulnerable to lone-actors attacks. To prevent this event-triggered motivation, security levels and resource allocation during these critical periods should be seriously considered.

Before concluding, it is important to note the main limitation of our analysis. The study of one method of terrorism at a specific locality, while chosen specifically to answer the problem of heterogeneity, may help understand general behavioural patterns, but requires us to be cautious when making generalizations regarding other localities and methods of lone terror attacks. Future studies should follow similar traits among other sub-groups of lone actors, examining the question of motivation on the personal, and not only the national level. While more common in Israel and the West Bank than in other parts of the world, we believe that the simplicity and effectivity of Vehicle-Borne as an attack method, and the high levels of encouragement that this method has received, are likely to lead to an increase in the

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numbers of this kind of attack in Europe and the US. Future studies should therefore go beyond the profile of attackers to examine the characteristics and decision-making process related to the attack, increasing our ability to prevent and mitigate this form of terrorism.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Attacker's age group

Age group	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-25	33	53.2	53.2
26-33	12	19.4	72.6
34-41	11	17.7	90.3
42-49	1	1.6	91.9
Above 49	5	8.1	100
Total	62	100	

Table 2: Attacker's personal characteristics

Offender's personal characteristics	Yes	No	Total
Was the offender male?	59	3	100%
Was the offender over 18 years old?	62	0	100%
Was the offender married or living with a spouse?	29	14	69.3%
Did the offender have children?	23	20	69.3%
Did the offender have high-school education or higher?	13	13	41.9%
Did the offender have previous criminal convictions?	17	16	53.2%
Was the offender arrested as a juvenile?	9	17	41.9%
Was the offender previously imprisoned?	10	52	100%

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Was the offender's socio-economic status equal to or higher than average?	40	19	95.1%
Did the offender have a known mental condition?	8	24	51.6%
Did the offender have previous military experience?	0	42	67.7%
Did the offender engage in violent behavior previous to the attack?	18	9	43.5%
Was the attacker a religious/conservative Muslim?	60	2	100%

Figure 1: Previous criminal/terrorist activity

Figure 2: Evidence of a “tipping point” preceding the attack

Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

Appendix Vehicle-Borne lone-actor terrorist attacks in Israel, January 2000-March 2016

S/N	Attacker's name	Date	Location
1	Ahmed Abu-Alouh	1.10.2000	East Jerusalem
2	Halil Abu Eilba	14.2.2001	Israel
3	Wahal Abu-Hamdan	1.3.2001	West Bank
4	Unknown	25.3.2001	West Bank
5	Majed Abu Saada	28.1.2002	West Bank
6	Hasam Dwait	2.7.2008	Israel
7	Rassan Abu-Tir	22.7.2008	Israel
8	Qassam Mugrabi	22.9.2008	Israel
9	Sammed Katabi	27.12.2008	East Jerusalem
10	Merai Redaidda	5.3.2009	Israel
11	Muhammad Salem Mossa Aabdin	18.4.2009	West Bank
12	Ziad Juliani	11.6.2010	East Jerusalem
13	Islam Ibraheam Eissa	15.5.2011	Israel
14	Mohammad Tsofan	29.8.2011	Israel
15	Issa Harub	11.12.2011	West Bank
16	Arkan Badir	9.9.2012	West Bank
17	Rami Shakirat	23.12.2012	East Jerusalem
18	Yunes Radaida	17.10.2013	East Jerusalem

Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

				West Bank
				West Bank
19	Itsam Aadi	15.3.2014		
20	Ra'ed jaabari	25.7.2014		
21	Mhammad Ga'abis	4.8.2014	Israel	
22	Abed A-Rachman Shaludi	22.10.2014	Israel	
23	Hammam Jamal Badui Massalame	5.11.2014		West Bank
24	Ibrahim Samir Skafi	4.11.2014		West Bank
25	Ibrahim Aakari	5.11.2014	Israel	
26	Maher Hashalmon (event 1)	10.11.2014		West Bank
27	Maher Hashalmon (event 2)	10.11.2014		West Bank
28	Sameh Zuheir Mahmud Shusha	8.2.2015		West Bank
29	Mahmmad (Mahmod) Slaimma	6.3.2015		West Bank
30	Haled Kutaina	15.4.2015	Israel	
31	Fadi Tzalach	25.4.2015	East Jerusalem	
32	Amran Amar Abu Dahim	20.5.2015	East Jerusalem	
33	Raaid Muhammad Ibrahim Bduann	6.8.2015		West Bank
34	Allah Ziwad	11.10.2015		West Bank
35	Allah Abu Jamal	13.10.2015	Israel	

Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

			West Bank
			West Bank
36	Hamzeh Moussa al-Amleh	20.10.2015	West Bank
37	Muhammad Shlalda	21.10.2015	West Bank
38	Ahmmad Yakin Yousef Jabari	1.11.2015	West Bank
39	Thrwat Aibrhaim El-Sharawi	5.11.2015	West Bank
40	Suliman Shahin	8.11.2015	
41	Mohammed Abdel Basset al-Kharoub	19.11.2015	
42	Shadi Muhammad Mahmad Hatzib	22.11.2015	West Bank
43	Azmi Nafa Diyah	24.11.2015	West Bank
44	Fadi Hassib	27.11.2015	West Bank
45	Umar A-Zakik	27.11.2015	West Bank
46	Anas Hammad	4.12.2015	West Bank
47	Amar Yasser Skaffi	6.12.2015	Israel
48	Muhammad Abed El-Halim	10.12.2015	West Bank
49	Ahmed Hassan Jahajha	16.12.2015	West Bank
50	Hikmat Farouq Hamdan	16.12.2015	West Bank
51	Muhammad Abd al-Rahman Ayyad	18.12.2015	West Bank
52	Jalal Shuman	18.12.2015	West Bank

Vehicle-Borne attackers in Israel and the West Bank

				West Bank
				West Bank
53	Wissam Abu Oila	24.12.2015	West Bank	
54	Mahadia Hmad	25.12.2015	West Bank	
55	Mahar Jabbi	25.12.2015	West Bank	
56	Hassan Ali Hassan Bazur	31.12.2015	West Bank	
57	Abed Raad Abdallah Hamad	19.2.2016	West Bank	
58	Amani Husenni Sabatin	4.3.2016	West Bank	
59	Amir Fuad Naaim Aljendi	14.3.2016	West Bank	
60	Muhammad Yosef Ahmand Arpheia	14.5.2015		West Bank 61
	Qassam Frid Abed Al-Aziz Jabber	14.3.2016		
62	Yousef Walid Matsafa Traira	14.3.2016		

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¹ Anthony Bond, "Nice terrorist attack: ISIS leader told supporters to 'run over the filthy French' in chilling threat," *The Mirror*, July 15, 2016.

² Paul Gill, *Lone-actor terrorists: A behavioural analysis* (Routledge, 2015).

³ Some examples are: Edwin Bakker and Beatrice De Graaf, "Preventing lone wolf terrorism: Some CT approaches addressed," *Perspectives on Terrorism* 5(5-6) (2011);

Ramón Spaaij, "The enigma of lone wolf terrorism: An assessment," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 33(9) (2010): 854-870; Ramon Spaaij, *Understanding lone wolf terrorism: Global patterns, motivations and prevention*. (Springer Science & Business Media, 2011); Ramón Spaaij and Mark S. Hamm, "Key issues and research agendas in lone wolf terrorism," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 38(3) (2015): 167-178; Jason-Leigh Striegler, "Early detection of the lone wolf: advancement of counterterrorism investigations with an absence or abundance of information and intelligence," *Journal of Policing, Intelligence and Counter Terrorism* 8(1) (2013): 35-53; Gabriel Weimann, "Lone wolves in cyberspace," *Journal of Terrorism Research* 3(2) (2012). DOI: <http://doi.org/10.15664/jtr.405>

⁴ Gill, *Lone-actor*, 26.

⁵ See Randy Borum, Robert Fein and Bryan Vossekuil, "A dimensional approach to analyzing lone offender terrorism," *Aggression and Violent Behavior* 17(5) (2012): 389-396.

⁶ See for example Gill, Paul, John Horgan, and Paige Deckert. "Bombing alone:

Tracing the motivations and antecedent behaviors of lone-actor terrorists." *Journal of forensic sciences* 59(2) (2014): 425-435; Nesser, Petter. "Research note: single actor terrorism: scope, characteristics and explanations." *Perspectives on Terrorism* 6(6) (2012).

⁷ Fred Burton and Scott Stewart, *The lone wolf disconnect* (Terrorism Intelligence Report-STRATFOR, 2008).

⁸ Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50.

⁹ Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50; Marc Sageman, *Understanding terror networks* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2004). ¹⁰ Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50; Randy Borum, Robert Fein and Bryan Vossekuil, "A dimensional approach to analyzing lone offender terrorism," *Aggression and Violent Behavior* 17(5) (2012): 389-396; Rik Coolsaet, ed., *Jihadi terrorism and the radicalisation challenge: European and American experiences* (Routledge, 2016).

¹¹ Gill, *Lone-actor*, 26.

¹² Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50; Paul Gill, John Horgan and Paige Deckert, "Bombing alone: Tracing the motivations and antecedent behaviors of lone-actor terrorists," *Journal of forensic sciences* 59(2) (2014): 425-435; Clark McCauley and Sophia Moskalenko, *Friction: How radicalization happens to them and us* (Oxford university Press, 2011); Clark McCauley and Sophia Moskalenko, "Toward a profile of lone wolf terrorists: What moves an individual from radical

opinion to radical action,” *Terrorism and Political Violence* 26(1) (2014): 69-85. ¹³

It is important to note that firearms are very accessible and easy to come by in the US, where most studies were conducted.

¹⁴ COT (ed.), Lone-Wolf Terrorism. Case study for Work Package 3 ‘Citizens and governance in a knowledge-based society’, TTSRL, July 2007, cf:

<http://www.transnationalterrorism.eu/tekst/publications/Lone-Wolf%20Terrorism.pdf>;

David C. Rapoport, “The four waves of modern terrorism,” *Attacking terrorism:*

Elements of a grand strategy (2004): 46-73; Spaaij, “The enigma”, 854-870.

¹⁵ Spaaij and Hamm, “Key issues”, 167-178.

¹⁶ Spaaij and Hamm, “Key issues”, 167-178.

¹⁷ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, “Bombing alone”, 425-435; Michael King and Donald M. Taylor, “The radicalization of homegrown jihadists: A review of theoretical models and social psychological evidence,” *Terrorism and Political Violence* 23(4) (2011): 602-622; Harvey W. Kushner, *The future of terrorism: violence in the new millennium* (Sage Publications, 1997); Lorenzo Vidino, “Homegrown jihadist terrorism in the United States: A new and occasional phenomenon?” *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 32(1) (2009): 1-17.

¹⁸ Emily Corner and Paul Gill, “A false dichotomy? Mental illness and lone-actor terrorism,” *Law and human behavior* 39(1) (2015): 23.

¹⁹ Bakker and De Graaf, “Preventing lone-wolf”, 43-50; Jeff Gruenewald, Steven

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Chermak and Joshua D. Freilich, "Distinguishing "loner" attacks from other domestic extremist violence," *Criminology & Public Policy* 12(1) (2013): 65-91; Sophia Moskalenko and Clark McCauley, "The psychology of lone-wolf terrorism," *Counselling Psychology Quarterly* 24(2) (2011): 115-126; Jonathan Rae, "Will it ever be possible to profile the terrorist?" *Journal of Terrorism Research* 3(2) (2012).

²⁰ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, "Bombing alone", 425-435.

²¹ Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50; Gill, *Lone-actor*, 120; Gill, Horgan and Deckert, "Bombing alone", 425-435.

²² Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50.

²³ Steven M. Chermak, Joshua D. Freilich, William S. Parkin and James P. Lynch, "American terrorism and extremist crime data sources and selectivity bias: An investigation focusing on homicide events committed by far-right extremists," *Journal of Quantitative Criminology* 28(1) (2012): 191-218; Andrew Silke, "The devil you know: Continuing problems with research on terrorism," *Terrorism and political violence* 13(4) (2001): 1-14.

²⁴ e.g. Daveed Gartenstein-Ross, "Lone Wolf Islamic Terrorism: Abdulhakim Mujahid Muhammad (Carlos Bledsoe) Case Study," *Terrorism and Political Violence* 26(1) (2014): 110-128; McCauley and Moskalenko, "Toward a profile," 69-85.

²⁵ Gill, *Lone-actor*, 26; Gill, Horgan and Deckert, "Bombing alone", 425-435.

²⁶ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, "Bombing alone", 433.

²⁷ Randy Borum, Robert Fein and Bryan Vossekuil, "A dimensional approach to analyzing lone offender terrorism," *Aggression and Violent Behavior* 17(5) (2012):

389-396.

²⁸ Marc Sageman, *Understanding terror networks* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2004).

²⁹ For example, on-line communities.

³⁰ McCauley and Moskalenko, "Toward a profile," 69-85.

³¹ Bakker and De Graaf, "Preventing lone-wolf", 43-50.

³² Raffaello Pantucci, *A typology of lone wolves: Preliminary analysis of lone Islamist terrorists* (London, England: International Centre for the Study of Radicalisation and Political Violence, 2011).

³³ e.g., tragedy or a need to revenge.

³⁴ Pantucci, *A typology*, 8.

³⁵ Gill, *Lone-actor*, 120.

³⁶ Jeanine De Roy van Zuijdewijn and Edwin Bakker, "Analysing Personal characteristics of Lone-Actor Terrorists: Research Findings and Recommendations,"

Perspectives on Terrorism 10(2) (2016).

³⁷ Ronald Victor Gemuseus Clark and Graeme R. Newman, *Outsmarting the terrorists* (Greenwood Publishing Group, 2006).

³⁸ Marcus Felson and Ronald V. Clarke, "Opportunity makes the thief," *Police research series*, 98 (1998); Ronald Victor Gemuseus Clarke and Derek B. Cornish, "Rational Choice: Explaining criminals and crime essays," (2001).

³⁹ Joshua D. Freilich and Steven M. Chermak, “Preventing deadly encounters between law enforcement and American far-rightists,” *Crime Prevention Studies* 25(1) (2009):

141-172; Leslie W. Kennedy, *Applying Crime Theory to Terrorism Research: Contemporary Issues in Criminal Justice Policy* (Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage Learning, 2010): 129-131.

⁴⁰ Borum, Fein and Vossekul, “A dimensional approach”, 389-396.

⁴¹ Clarke and Newman, *Outsmarting the terrorists*, 31-41.

⁴² e.g. Gary A. Ackerman and Lauren E. Pinson, “An army of one: Assessing CBRN pursuit and use by lone wolves and autonomous cells,” *Terrorism and Political Violence* 26(1) (2014): 226-245; Gill, Horgan and Deckert, “Bombing alone”, 425-435.

⁴³ The complete list of events is presented in the Appendix.

⁴⁴ Gill, *Lone-actor*, 120.

⁴⁵ In Israel, court files are open to the public, and can often be accessed on-line.

⁴⁶ “The use of the internet for terrorist purposes United Nations,” the United Nations 2012, accessed March 13, 2016, http://www.unodc.org/documents/frontpage/Use_of_Internet_for_Terrorist_Purposes.pdf

⁴⁷ Thomas J. Holt, “Exploring the intersections of technology, crime, and terror,” *Terrorism and Political Violence* 24(2) (2012): 337-354; Gartenstein-Ross, “Lone

Wolf Islamic Terrorism”, 110-128; Andre Oboler, “Google Earth: A new platform for anti-Israel propaganda and replacement geography,” *Jerusalem Centre for Public Affairs* 8(5) (2008): 26; Weimann, “Lone wolves,” 75-90.

⁴⁸ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, “Bombing alone”, 425-435.

⁴⁹ We can assume that the level of education is also correlated to the employment of most of the Vehicle-Borne attackers as professional drivers.

⁵⁰ The statistical test utilized the number of injured as an indicator of lethality of the attack since the number of injured was significantly larger than the number of victims. ⁵¹ Victoroff, Jeff. "The mind of the terrorist: A review and critique of psychological approaches." *Journal of Conflict resolution* 49(1) (2005): 3-42.

⁵² Bakker and De Graaf, “Preventing lone-wolf”, 43-50; Corner and Gill, “A false dichotomy”, 23.

⁵³ Meloy, J. Reid, and Paul Gill. "The lone-actor terrorist and the TRAP-18." *Journal of Threat Assessment and Management* 3(1) (2016): 37. Pantucci, Raffaello. "What have we learned about lone wolves from Anders Behring Breivik?." *Perspectives on Terrorism* 5(5-6) (2011).

⁵⁴ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, “Bombing alone”, 425-435.

⁵⁵ Gill, Horgan and Deckert, “Bombing alone”, 425-435.

⁵⁶ Spaaij and Hamm, “Key issues”, 167-178.